

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

JOURNAL OF TERTIARY AND INDUSTRIAL SCIENCES

A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF THE HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS'
TRAINING COLLEGE, KUMBA

VOLUME 3, NUMBER 2
JULY, 2023

PUBLISHER:
HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS' TRAINING COLLEGE (HTTC)
UNIVERSITY OF BUEA

P.O Box: 249 Buea Road, Kumba
Tel: (+237) 33354691 – Fax: (+237) 33354692
Email: editorinchief@httckumba.com
Website: <http://www.httckumba.com>

EDITORIAL BOARD

Supervision:

Professor Ngomo Horace Manga
University of Buea

Editor-in-Chief:

Prof. Akume Daniel Akume, University of Buea, Cameroon

Associate Editors:

Prof. Ebune B. Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Defang Henry, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Lissouck Daniel, University of Buea, Cameroon

Advisory Editors:

Prof. Tabi Johannes Atemnkeng, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Fonteh Athanasius Amungwa, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Lyonga N. Agnes Ngale, University of Buea, Cameroon

Members of the Editorial Board:

Prof. Yamb Belle Emmanuel, University of Douala, Cameroon
Prof. Ambe Njoh Jonathan, University of South Florida, USA
Prof. John Akande, Bowen University, Nigeria
Prof. Talla Pierre Kisito, University of Dschang, Cameroon
Prof. Rosemary Shafack, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Njimanted Godfrey Forgha, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Prof. Nzalie Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Mouange Ruben, IUT University of Ngaoundere, Cameroon
Prof. Boum Alexander, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Patrick Wanyu Kongnyuy, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Prof. Tchuen Ghyslain, IUT Badjoun, University of Dschang, Cameroon
Prof. Rose Frii-Manyi Anjoh, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Foadieng Emmanuel, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Tchinda Rene, IUT Badjoun, University of Dschang, Cameroon
Prof. Tabi Pascal Tabot, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Katte Valentine, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Prof. Zinkeng Martina, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Obama Belinga Christian Theophile, University of Ebolowa, Cameroon
Prof. Nkongho Anyi Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Cordelia Givechek Kometa, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Ngouateu Wouagfack Paiguy, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Tchakoutio Alain, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Morfaw Bertrand, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Tamba Gaston, IUT University, Douala, Cameroon
Prof. Koumi Simon, ENS, Ebolowa, University of Yaounde I
Prof. Ajongakoh Raymond, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Ntabe Eric, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Abanda Henry Fonbiyen, Oxford Brookes University, UK
Dr. Luis Alberto Torrez Cruz, University of Witwatersrand, South Africa
Dr. Negou Ernest, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Aloyem Kaze Claude Vidal, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Mfombep Priscilla Mebong, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Asoba Gillian, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Bahel Benjamin, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Agbortoko Ayuk Nkem, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Mouzong Pemi, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Orock Fidelis Tanyi, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Wanie Clarkson Mvo, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Dr. Molombe Jeff Mbella, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Emmanuel Tata Sunjo, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Ndi Roland Akoh, University of Yaounde I, Cameroon
Dr. Kinfack Juetsa Aubin, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Kamda Silapeux Aristide, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Roland Ndah Njoh, University of Buea, Cameroon

Table of Contents

STUDY AND DESIGN OF A FOUR-PORTS HYBRID SOLAR/WIND DC-DC CONVERTER	1
Boukar Miri ¹ , Aloyem Kaze Claude ¹ , Ajamah Ferdinand ¹ , Tchouga Tchao Yannick ² , Ngouateu paigui ¹	
EXPERIMENTAL STUDY AND MULTISCALE NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF CRACKS IN VISCOELASTIC MATERIALS: APPLICATION TO BILINGA (NAUCLEADIDEERRICHI)	18
Mbelle Samuel Bisong* ^{1,2} , Tawe laynde ³ , Francois Njock Bayock ² , Valeriy V. Lepov ^{4,5} , Pierre Kisito Talla 6	
HARVESTING COMPOUNDS THE EFFECT OF WATER DEFICIT ON THE GROWTH AND YIELD OF WATER LEAF [TALINUM TRIANGULARE (JACQ.) WILLD.]	42
Dekoum VM Assaha* ¹ , Awasume Clovis Awasume ¹ , Pascal Tabi Tabot ¹ , Priscilla Mebong Mfombep ¹	
GEOLOCATION AND STUDY OF HOUSEHOLD WELL WATER IN RELATION TO CONTAMINANTS AS HEALTH MAPPING TOOL IN KUMBA, SOUTH WEST REGION, CAMEROON	55
BAHEL Benjamin ^{1,2} , NGWEM Bayiha Blaise ³ , Bate Esame Bate ¹ , NDIVE Martin Molua ¹ , Lissouck Daniel ⁴ , YAMB Emmanuel ³	
ANTHROPOMORPHISM AND GREEN ECONOMY: A STUDY OF JOHN NKEMNGONG NKENGASONG'S ANCESTRAL EARTH	72
Fomin Edward Efuet (Ph.D.)	
HUMAN EVOLUTION IN AFRICA AND GENETIC VARIATION: A GENETIC HISTORIAN'S INTERPRETATION	92
Forka Leypey Mathew Fomine	
THE PRAGMATICS OF CAMEROON ENGLISH	110
Menge Aaron Tabe	
FORMULATION OF A SNAIL-PROTEIN RICH MAIZE BASE WEANING FOOD (NutriPACK)	122
Samuel Metuge ^{1,2,3} , Asoba Gillian Nkeudem ^{1,2} , Tabe Frida Bawak ¹ , Ngede Laura Senge ¹ , Teh Rene Ning ² , Sumbele Irene Ule Ngole ²	
FORMULATION OF A YOGHURT LIKE PRODUCT FROM CORN MILK, SOY BEANS MILK, SKIMMED MILK ENRICHED WITH BANANA FLAVOUR	135
Mateing Cindry, Fidelis Sameh Ebong* ¹ , Asoba. Gilian Mofor ²	

CUSTOMER ATTRACTION AND RETENTION STRATEGIES IN VERY SMALL BUSINESSES: CASE OF BUTCHERIES IN LIMBE, CAMEROON	152
Ndoko Alice Ekoi, Negou Ernest* ² , Nkenganyi Fonkem Marcellus ³	

**ANTHROPOMORPHISM AND GREEN ECONOMY: A STUDY OF JOHN
NKEMNGONG NKENGASONG'S ANCESTRAL EARTH**

By

Fomin Edward Efuet (Ph.D.)

fominedward@yahoo.com

**Department of English and Cultural Studies
Faculty of Arts
University of Buea**

Abstract

Environmental protection from ongoing hazards geared towards a sustainable development of natural species the world over has become a topical issue affecting human environment today. Humanity in this dispensation is living in a world characterized by mankind's unquenchable thirst to reign as King of Creation with the desire to be considered superior to all other non-human species. This study is intended to condemn such a practice and rather intensify education on the possibilities to which mankind, as evident in Nkengasong's Ancestral Earth needs to reviewed his/her strategies towards relating with environmental non-human species as a way to ensure effective species management and sustainability. The research is predicated on the contention that Mankind, through his arrogance towards nature, either consciously or unconsciously, is the cause of his own predicament, especially in this era of environmental hazards and degradation. The work is informed by ecocriticism as a theory of literary criticism. It argues that the continuous prowess of environmental natural species on the one hand and humanity's unethical Behavior towards the environment on the other, as well as the possible way forward towards ameliorating mankind's thorny environmental hazards are the crux of the matter in this study and in all human responsibilities towards ensuring a more sustainable species development.

Keywords: *Anthropomorphism, Green Economy, Sustainable development, Environmental ethics, Anthropocentrism, Greenhouse gases, Global Warming.*

1 Introduction

Caring for the environment has become a topical issue plaguing the world today, the intention being to ensure ecological prowess and sustainable development of species therein. Mankind's activities on planet earth either consciously or unconsciously through logging, poaching, polluting of land, water and air spaces and more have all created undesirable environmental hazards such as greenhouse gases, global warming, extinction and or near extinction of some animal and plant species, uncontrollable health hazards, increase in flood occurrences in many parts of the world today and a lot more. This precarious state of our contemporary environment has intermittently attracted environmentally conscious critics (ecocritics) into a series of conferences and summits (Kyoto protocol in 1997, the Copenhagen summit of 2009, COP 21 in Paris 2015, United Nations Climate Change Conference and Sustainable Development, 2014; Cop24 in Katowice, Poland, 2018, just to name these few). All these were in an attempt to find out means in combatting to reduce the amount of gas emission by the different highly industrialized countries in the world and also to regulate some environmental excesses. These conferences and summits have perhaps not yielded the desired fruits since the situation continues to aggravate as seen in the increase number of floods, increase in global warming and frequent draught in many parts of the world today, increase in complicated health hazards and a lot more undesirable environmental challenges occurring on the planet earth. The situation is further aggravated by the highly industrialized countries not respecting the terms of reducing their gas emissions, but rather continuously exploiting with impunity the little forest left in Africa, Asia, South America and a few other areas, not caring the global hazardous and imminent consequences.

In his text *Ancestral Earth*, John Nkemngong Nkengasong discusses what to him could be some of the causes and perhaps possible solutions to these environmental hazardous challenges. His analysis which we are going to examine from an ecological conscious perspective helps in a way to reawaken his readers on how they could ameliorate on the socio-political and economic lots that provoke environmental ills. This, according to him could be done through becoming more environmentally conscious or by putting on anthropomorphic lenses in environmental reflections and interactions. In other words, he uses ecocriticism as a weapon to condemn the socio-political and economic actions of mankind that prohibit the growth of the natural environmental species or act as a deterrent to ecological prowess.

Key concepts to be defined in this study are: "Anthropomorphism" and "Green Economy". This study adopts Lawrence Buell's definition for the two concepts. Buell defines anthropomorphism as "...the attribution of human feelings or traits to non-human beings or objects or natural phenomena" (134). He further argues that anthropomorphism is the projection human desire to make nature sympathise with humankind or oppositely, it might be done in the interest of dramatizing the claims or plight of the natural world.

Anthropomorphism therefore preaches the notion of giving human qualities to animate or non-living species. If this was to be effectively implemented, humanity will have a lot of respect for natural non-human species and consequently, environmental or natural species sustainability will be a dream realised. On the other hand, he (Lawrence Buell) defines “green economy” as “...a study that gestures towards biological science and to the natural as against the built environment” (138). Green economy, he notes, focuses on nature writing, wilderness studies and an environmental commitment in a socio-centric direction. Green economy, like ecocriticism therefore preaches environmental natural species and mankind’s interaction with them. Both have the same strengths at the centre of the universe and ecocritics feel that mankind should not use his/her advantage over the other. The critical framework adopted for the analysis of the study is ecocriticism. This is a critical literary theory propounded by ecocritics like Cheryll Glotfelty, Harold Fromm, Nancy Cook, Lawrence Buell, Greg Garrard and many others. These critics have in their different critical works defined ecocriticism using different words. A working definition of ecocriticism for this study however, will be taken from Cheryll Glotfelty who defines the concept as a study of the relationship between Literature and the physical environment. According to her, ecocriticism studies the way man functions in relation to environment; the way man interacts with the physical or natural environment at his disposal in a bid to ascertain his/her degree of eco-friendly and or eco sceptical with nature.

This study is intended among other things, to examine the extent to which Nkengasong in *Ancestral Earth* fights against the vulnerability of environmental natural species. It also projects mankind’s unethical Behavior towards the environment and the possible way forward for amelioration. It is predicated on the contention that Mankind, through his arrogance towards nature, either consciously or unconsciously, is the cause of his own predicament, especially in this era of environmental hazards and degradation. I argue therefore that it is by keeping the environment in tact from destruction of its natural environmental species, that mankind can attain his/her height of sustainable development and a healthy environment worth human habitation.

2 Review of existing literature

From empirical perspective, not much has been written on Nkengasong’s *Ancestral Earth*. Florence Mbobu Ngie (2019) in her paper entitled “Gender and the Politics of Power/ Powerlessness in John Nkengasong’s *Ancestral Earth* studies the text by critiquing and challenging the Eurocentric notion which says that Africa has no history. She questions the school of thought which uses Eurocentric standards to rate Africa’s Underdevelopment, She rather accuses the west for initiating corruption, exploitation of Africa’s natural resources and more ills as a strategy for under developing Africa. She further argues that African women like their male counterpart understand natural roles and act accordingly, Gender issues raised in the play she notes, are part and parcel of African

history. Nkengasong as well as his contemporaries' works could be read as alternatives, critiquing or resistance to oppressive canons that lead to new found tenable canons.

From the conceptual point of view, Nkemngong Nkengasong (2020) on his part in his paper entitled "Was Anything Wrong with Worshiping Green Gods? Sacred Ecology and Indigenous Environmental Ethics in Cameroonian writing", writes about the rapid degradation of the environment and its impact on the indigenous ecocultural relations and how this has been a significant concern to several Cameroonian writers. This scholar sees this as a controversy opposing both the myths-oriented and scientific vested opinions to determine the cause of the disaster which according to him is still unsettled. Many scholars on contemporary writings have reacted variously to the unchecked deterioration of the ecology and its impact on sustainable management of the resources and the cultural life of the people.

Similarly, Fomin Edward Efuat (2021) in his paper entitled "Green Economy and Sustainable Development: An Ecological Reading of Athanasius Nsahlai's *The Buffalo Rider* investigates and analyses the extent to which Nso people of Cameroon have contributed in ensuring sustainable green economy in their environment. The paper argues that humankind needs to take a radical stance to ensure that the 21st century environment is challenged, re-defined and re-positioned with regards to changing realities like population growth, more technological advancements and their consequences. The paper further challenges Nso people for exercising environmental scepticism in this era in which the preaching of human and environmental friendliness is nowadays a common practice.

This paper departs from the works reviewed in that it studies the text (*Ancestral Earth*) from the point of view of Anthropomorphism challenges. It examines the extent to which humankind values the place of non-human species in the environment in a bid to investigate what could be done to ensure increase species sustainability. This is a niche that no scholar has worked on in this text.

2.1 Environmental Hazards in *Ancestral Earth*

Environmental natural species are exposed to risk as Mankind uses them indiscriminately, consciously or unconsciously, to satisfy his numerous hungering needs. This is evident in human action in Nkengasong's *Ancestral Earth*. In this era where anthropomorphic consciousness is gradually gaining ground in many environmental debates anthropocentric practices like the one mentioned above is condemned in strong terms as a way to ensure species sustainability for posterity.

The text *Ancestral Earth* depicts a society known as Allehtendurih, ruled by Fon Akeumbin. The past of this society is characterized by rich Fiona and flora, accompanied by rich soils for agriculture, animal breeding and legendary hospitality of the people. Due to poor management of these natural resources as a result of logging, poaching, careless disposal of waste and a number of other ills, the community has undergone degradation in terms of species sustainability. This vulnerability in species management attracts

conflicts, hatred, hunger, health hazards and many more undesirable occurrences between the different segments of Allehtendurih community. Reconciliation, however, is finally reached to consolidate some of the plant species after a voice, supposedly of the ancestors, calls every defaulter (including Fon Akeumbin, the women and children of Allehtendurih) one after the other, cautioning them on the need to protect the environment and its species for sustainable development.

Mafua and M'meka, representatives of the women of Allehtendurih, using action and dialogue, lament about the macabre situation in which the women of the clan with their numerous children and respective husbands find themselves in, meanwhile the Fon makes no effort to ameliorate their situation. Mafua notes thus:

Here we have arrived at the palace of Allehtendurih, where Akeumbin, our Fon, the descendant of Anyankendong must tell us if this earth on which our feet stand is the same in which our mothers buried our umbilical cords And even when we scratch the soil into tumid mounds, the crops laugh at our endeavours The streams are sour: They are dry. We do not have water to drink. We can no longer fish the tadpoles and the crabs to pound fufu for our husbands. (3 and 4)

M'meka then retorts thus: "And yet our Fon, man beyond man and our husbands do not scratch a pimple on their skin even when the soil continues to mock at our endeavours." (3 and 4) The complaint from women representatives shows how they (the women of Allehtendurih) have been relegated to the background by the Fon and their respective husbands. The plight of these women, characterized by confusion, doubt, and anger shows the catastrophe, not only caused by climate change on the environment but of domination and oppression of women by the patriarchal society of Allehtendurih. It is the genesis of the conflict of otherness, representation, domination and women resistance from male domination. If the environment of Allehtendurih is undergoing degradation it is due to the conflict of leadership and management. The women feel that something must be done to ensure soil fertility and increase yields. This will enable them to feed their families. The Fon on his part rebukes them, in a counter conflict considering their demands as an act of laziness and cowardice. He sends them out of his palace thereby provoking this conflict the more. This precarious situation of such actions with the accompanying exchange of bitter words in the above dialogue by members of the clan further reminds us of the contemporary hazardous state of climate change facing the entire world today; a situation which has brought untold sufferings, drought, global warming, and myriads of other hazards. Nkengasong feels that mankind needs to give value to the environmental species to ensure its sustainability.

Cheryll Glotfelty had long ago seen this state of environmental turbulence when she warned that:

We are facing a global crisis today, not because of how ecosystem functions but rather because of how our ethical system functions. Getting through the

crisis requires understanding our impact on nature as precisely as possible, but even more, it requires understanding those ethical systems and using that understanding to reform them". (2004).

Glotfelty feels that the environmental crisis we are going through is due to mankind's lack of ethics in environmental education and management; and consequently ignorant about the effects of his/her actions on the environment. Glotfelty insists on the education of the masses so that environmental degradation can be relegated to the background. In the context of our study, therefore, one could argue that Glotfelty might have been referring to the like of Fon Akeumbin and the husbands to the women of Allehtendurih who need a sound environmental education through which the environmental lots of Allehtendurih could be ameliorated.

The situation is further aggravated when M'meka further says: "...there are no clouds in the skies. And the sun burns our backs and brings us all the heat in the world (3) She is in effect confirming the presence of global warming with its undesirable effects on our environment; hazards that need to be eradicated fast. The dialogue, again, between Mafua and M'meka concerning the state of affairs in Allehtendurih leaves much to be desired in the socio-economic situation of that community as we listen to the two women representatives thus:

M'meka "... how we suffer to feed our homes, even when the soil frowns at us"

Mafua: "I harvested very few groundnuts and cocoyams last season. There wasn't anything to eat out of it".

M'meka: "Mafua, shall we survive on this earth for long?"

Mafua: The earth has changed its mind against us. Yet our husbands and the Fon sit like the stones that have nothing to do with hoes. (4)

The interaction between Mafua and M'meka on the relationship between earth and mankind shows the degree of attachment that mankind has for natural species and mother earth, either using them as means for food, shelter, clothing, or to satisfy other human needs. It shows the inseparable link between mankind and nature. From the economic perspective, it sparks conflict between the women and their husbands as each struggle to cling on the earth for survival. The women nevertheless get so disappointed and decry the system especially when their husbands and the Fon of Allehtendurih show indifference to their plight. They decide to speak out to ensure that the earth is appeased by their Fon (Akeumbin) as a pre-condition for good yields and an improvement in the social and economic strengths of Allehtendurih. When Mafua notes anthropomorphically that "the earth has changed its mind" it shows the unethical way through which humanity has been tapping unsustainably from it. M'meka notes about the Fon thus: "He must tell us today if this earth which aches our feet is the same earth our mothers used to praise in songs". (4-5). This statement reveals environmental degradation due to non-respect for environmental protection ethics. Esei corroborates the words of M'meka saying: "The soil is barren like a stone that has nothing to do with a woman's hoe. Trees have

disappeared ...” (8) Here Esei lays emphasis on the hazards the environment is going through due to unethical logging in Allehtendurih forest. This is a call for conscientization of humanity and his relationship with natural environment. This is further complicated as the Fon’s “red friends” (white men) provide him with a gun and he gives them order to exploit the forest under the pretext that it is a means of developing Allehtendurih to have the status of a city. This action which shows the Fon’s egocentric and pseudo anthropomorphic nature and his eco-sceptical worldview, further reveal imminent conflict between him and his Allehtendurih counterparts.

Nigel Dudley et al corroborate this thought concerning the disappearance of trees when they write about global concerns in the 1980s and the early 1990s, where forest conservation focused on the rapid rate of deforestation in tropical countries. They argue that “deforestation is only one half of a more complex problem of global forest management. Forest qualities were recognized to be as important an issue as the quality of forest remaining”. (2006, p.4) It becomes very clear that deforestation is one of the complex problems of global forest and perhaps environmental management plaguing the world today. Excessive deforestation does not only result to species extinction, it also result to health hazards due to climatic changes caused amongst other things by the effect of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere.

Condemning mankind’s activities which have pushed up to polluting the air-space with its undesirable health hazards, Nkengasong notes:

The air is heavy. All the smoke of burning and toxic matter have invaded the air. All the smell of bad things stand stiff in the air and there is little rain in the sky. The sun lashes my balding head and for many moons I have sneezed and coughed (sneezes) I am almost choking. (9)

The quotation echoes the ongoing deforestation which is characterized by intense sunshine with its multiple health hazards. Through the quotation, Nkengasong mimics air pollution emanating from bush fire, burning of environmental waste and smoke from industries. All these anthropocentric mechanisms lead to environmental pollution with its undesirable effects on plants and animal species. M’meke thus announces at different time: that: “My mbanya’s child is dead ooo! Death has snatched my mbanya’s only child ooo!” (11). “prolonged sneezes by Lebu” (10). “The sun burns our backs and brings us all the heat in the world” (3). Mafua corroborates by saying: “Even now my twins are dead in my womb, and the vomit of the living children is thin; their stool is watery like soup cooked by a mad woman” (3). M’meke further notes that: “My own children are hungry; they are sick and pale like the spirits” (3). In another instance Mafua pointed out again that: “The heat of the sun has brought our children many fevers and we can no more find medical herbs in the bushes.”(13) The above dialogue revealing these different cases of health hazards come as a result of mankind’s unethical management of environment in a sustainable manner. This has brought in not only unfavourable changes in climate but also poor yields in food production thereby hindering effective feeding of the ever

growing population of Allehtendurih. This further renders the people of Allehtendurih vulnerable to a myriad of undesirable health challenges. The absence of environmental education, the greedy nature of the Fon and the lazy nature of the men of Allehtendurih are contributing factors to the degrading nature of mother earth.

On carrying their message to the Fon, the women of Allehtendurih expect immediate intervention as a way to curb imminent catastrophe. They seem to have fore-sight of what their Fon and their husbands are short-sighted of. Hence M'meka warns:

M'meka: "We came to tell the father of our husbands that hunger and disease have invaded our homes. Our soup tastes sour and we can no more find a dry twig to gather even to heat our food"

Mafua: we can no more find the mushroom that spread on the bosom of the earth. (12)

These hazards act as warning to the Fon. It demonstrates the fact that the environment has not been fairly treated and this may cause the people dearly. The fact that some of the rare species of food items have almost completely disappeared shows the decadence of anthropocentrism as human frailty in environmental studies. This lack of sustainability of some species, places the younger generation at the disadvantage of environmental prowess. Pagiola et al. raise a similar argument about poor treatment of environmental species when they write about the forest thus: "Forests are under severe threat in many parts of the world. The loss of forest has been accompanied by a loss of the many valuable services that forest provides - such as regulation of hydrological flows and carbon sequestration and of the biodiversity they contain". (2002, p.1) Mankind therefore has really disrespected the forest. The rate at which forest is disappearing has got a lot of impact on the political, social and economic growth of many communities. Challenges like ozone layer depletion and greenhouse gases effect, drought and flood intensification in different parts of the world, global warming, disappearance of species, displacement of animal species to different habitats with undesirable repercussions and a lot more continue to plaque the environment. Those involved in logging are not necessarily educated enough to understand the effect of their actions on the environment and its species. Through this destruction of plants caused by anthropocentric consciousness, some natural species become completely extinct, a thing which ecocritics decry as they preach anthropomorphism and species sustainability.

The initial naivety to environmental exigencies by the Fon of Allehtendurih is what has pushed this community into this social quirk mire. According to Fon Akeumbin, the women of his clan are lazy and not willing to till the soil. When he declares: "I have with my foreign friends cut down the forest and opened the land ..." (13), it further confirms his naivety on environmental management. Cutting down the forest without planting new trees is amongst other reasons the cause of today's hazards like global warming, and its multiple undesirable effects When Akeumbin talks of foreign friends, it reminds us of foreign logging companies with their capitalistic and exploitative life styles. In this case

their main intention is to make money irrespective of the damage that might arise in the cause of this. Again the notion of domination, otherness and suppression by the foreign partner whom he later refers to them as his “red friends” become evident.

Anthropomorphically speaking, the earth is angry due to all the treatment it has gone through; and the only solution as proposed amongst others by Alabi is “to appease the earth”(13) The Fon refuses being that he (Fon) accuses Alabi of having an affair with Afingong the Fon’s new bride and has “turned a cold face towards him” (13). This act of anthropocentrism whereby man claims he is the lord of creation begins to reveal its adverse effects on environment at different levels. The Fon becomes so obsessed with his new bride (Afingong) as opposed to the problems faced by the entire community of Allehtendurih.

Fon Akeumbin’s naivety is also seen when he announces to Allehtendurih people that:

I think I am doing Allehtendurih much good. We had to put down the forest to make the land bright, so that anyone can see where he puts his leg. The world is changing so Allehtendurih must change too. That is what the red people from faraway land told me. Do you not see how bright the land looks? ...
Even the Redman has abandoned his country and pleads to live here. (15)

The above quotation reminds us of the “redman’s” (Whiteman) desire and strategies to always dominate. It reminds us of their cunning and unreliable attitude. His strategy amongst other things is one of creating new forms of enslaving the Africans as a way to always keep them under bondage. Achebe as a visionary had thus warned: “The Whiteman is very clever ...” (1962.p.124). It is his witty nature that enables him to be able to have total control of continuous manipulation over the Africans. We find that cutting down trees just to make the land to look bright is a poorly conceived notion proposed by the Whiteman as a strategy not only to exploit timber, but of continuous domination. The Fon accepting the idea especially in this era where deforestation is being condemned shows his naivety and ignorance about environmental species management and sustainability. The Fon is working under the influence of materialistic benefits from his friends “Red people”. Here we can say Akeumbin does a bad thing (cutting down the forest) for a good reason (trying to develop the land). It is true that every society needs to move forward through changes; but the changes must be well reflected upon such that they impact the society positively. That is why Alabi, a visionary and one of the custodians of culture in Allehtendurih, condemns Akeumbin in strong terms. He argues that Akeumbin’s action is tantamount to auctioning the land to strangers, destroying the trees of life, just with the intention of gaining a gun as compensation. In return, upon all these ills, Akeumbin declares: “I have done no harm” (15) to the land and the people. This is sacrilegious, and points to lack of environmental education or consciousness.

William Raymond, an environmental critic, cautions mankind concerning his interaction with the environment when he argues that eco-culture studies should remain politically committed and academically engaged. “In this manner, eco-cultural analysis will help us

understand and make sense of cultural texts and products that have created nature as varied and variable ... as changing conditions of human world" (qtd. William Raymond, 1980, p. 85). This quotation acts as an appeal to environmental stakeholders to give environmental education and ecological sustainability the value they deserve. It is only through this that Akeumbin and his peers involved in environmental management will leave behind a rich ecological wealth for posterity. William Raymond thinks that environmental sustainability cannot be achieved without the political will and educational concern of stakeholders. This will help to change and re-orientate the way people relate to nature as an inevitable component of our daily life. It is as a result of Akeumbin's lack of environmental education and consciousness, (Anthropomorphism) that he, the author intimates, has reduced the land from a onetime song of joyful and robust men, women and children, pulsed with life whose land was filled with the wealth of nations and whose mountains the leopard snarled with pride and the lions roared with verve in the jungle, to what remains today as a land empty and bare of such memorable wealth for the land. It was a land, Alabi notes, with springs and streams, pure and healthy flooding into Antique River, rich forest and more. He consoles himself by hoping that Akeumbin must be brought to consciousness.

Alabi summarizes the hazards and the inconveniences of Allehtendurih in the midst of the ongoing environmental challenges in these words which reveal the unethical, unconscious, uneducated and unsustainable Behavior of the leadership of Allehtendurih. He notes:

The forest and the lands of Allehtendurih wither. The mountains stand like sore in the eye of the sun, the streams dry up, the air chokes and the red strangers are there digging up things only gods alone know and carting them away to their country, cutting down trees and destroying our totems as if they have heard the world was coming to an end so soon. And the children of Allehtendurih are dying.

Akeumbin, I cannot feel the warmth of this earth any more. (16)

This lamentation of the present vulnerable nature of Allehtendurih as opposed to its wonderful past glories contrasts Alabi and Akeumbin in terms of environmental worldview. Here Alabi is projected as one who is environmentally very conscious, ecologically sound and as one guided by the spirit of ecocentrism. Measuring the past glories and ecological prowess of Allehtendurih in terms of forest, mountains, streams, sun, trees and earth, indicate to an extent the drain of our rich resources amongst others by the people Akeumbin calls "red strangers" . Here Nkengasong reveals the colonial experience of extortion of Africa's rich resources to the west; destroying Africa's land and rich natural landscape with its endangered species in the course of doing this. From the quotation, the Whiteman's strategy of continuous exploitation of the riches of African continent is brought to the limelight. This attitude further corroborates what Chinua Achebe had decried in the attitude of the Whiteman's smartness and intelligence thus:

He came quietly and peaceably with his religion. We were amused at his foolishness and allowed him to stay. Now he has won our brothers and our clan can no longer act as one. He has put a knife on the things that held us together and we have fallen apart". (1962, p.124).

Achebe had foreseen the exploitative spirits of the Whiteman. He (Whiteman), Achebe argues, is so sly, cunning, pretentious, exploitative and convincing in character. He regularly develops new strategies through which he exploits to satisfy his ego. That is why he (Whiteman) easily wins Fon Akeumbin confidence when they offer him a gun and promise him that they intend to develop Allehtendurih; and to do this they start to cut down trees in the land. This is an intelligent way through which they intend to exploit the natural species in this environment. Through ignorance, and perhaps greed, Fon Akeumbin almost sacrificed his people, until resistance from them restored the land with hopes of a better future. As a consequence of the over exploitation of the land, Mafua reports that: "the partridge that used to sing in the woods is heard no more" (16). This is practically due to deforestation (logging) and poaching. This has sent not only partridges but also other wild animals of different endangered species far away from human habitation into the wilderness. This change of habitat cannot take place without some undesirable happenings on some of the species. In the same vein, logging has enabled some trees of endangered nature to disappear. It has caused climate change with its adverse effects on plant and animal species.

Akeumbin in the guise of a tragic hero finally regains consciousness and comes to realize his flaw in his Allehtenduruh community. In an action characterized by pathos for the Fon and his people, Akeumbin acknowledges before his people that: "I am a shadow, you cannot deceive me. There is no substance in me if the roar of a lion will not make the rat panic. There is no substance in me." (21). This message of a quest for pardon from Akeumbin is symbolic of regret for his past actions to his people and to the land; a wish for retributive justice concerning what he has done to nature and the opportunity for him to reconcile with nature and its species. He confesses his misdeeds in these words wherein he asks for forgiveness: "I am the only mad man in Allehtendurih I have offended you beyond reproach. Forgive me children of Allehtendurih. Forgive me fathers of the earth". (22) This shows his wish for the economy to be rebuilt so that it reflects what Allehtendurih used to be in the past. This can only be done amongst other things by him resisting from the white man's domination

As Akeumbin comes to realization, and sees the need for eco-consciousness, benefits of green economy and anthropomorphism to be preached in Allehtendurih, there is appeasement done through the mouth piece of Alabi. He calls and urges the line of ancestors of Allehtendurih who now dwell in the earth as ancestors to intervene in the people's (of Allehtendurih) misdeeds. He pleads on the ancestors for food, peace, love and happiness thus: "we have come to tell you that the earth has abandoned us. Our rich black earth bleeds and we feel the pains. Pity us father and bring us life again." (23)

Akeumbin's intransigence, lack of fore-sight and his astute nature as a leader towards nature and his people has brought him to this precarious situation where he is struggling to come out. This shows that human strength can only be successfully achieved when mankind moves closer to nature. When the author says anthropomorphically that the earth bleeds, it speaks volumes about the relationship between humanity and mother earth. The earth is a source of food, a source of water, our habitation, and a lot more. The need to consolidate such a relationship (mother earth and mankind) forced the ancestors to warn through a voice in these words:

Akeumbin, your greed and pride have made me shudder. You do not resemble the colour of this earth. You invited red strangers to barb the head of the earth with a keen knife and the children of Allehtendurih mourn and even when they mourn, you smear the priest of Fuandem with lies and shame. Akeumbin, what have you done to Allehtendurih? Why have you wounded the heart of the earth?
(23)

In the above quotation with its anthropomorphic orientation, Akeumbin's eco-scepticism is brought to the limelight. When he talks of "red strangers", it is suggestive of white men. The different logging companies are responsible for barbing the head of the earth with their instruments for felling trees "keen Knife". This act of deforestation has caused Allehtendurih quite much in terms of barrenness of the land, famine, poverty, health hazards, conflicts and more. It is a strategy of continuous domination through instituting hazards on the land. The voice of the ancestors in the above quotation reveals another level of resistance of Allehtendurih people from the Whiteman's domination through his different strategies put in place. It is hoped that this reconciliation with the earth will restore the past glories of the land (Allehtendurih).

The ancestral voice further notes as an attack on the women concerning their own negative contribution in destroying the land thus: "Women of Allehtendurih, You too have ruined the earth. You have burned so many fires and given us too much heat in the earth and we have wondered restlessly looking for another world to live in" (24). The different activities of humankind in the environment therefore have caused the ancestors much discomfort in their habitat. The voice therefore pleads that mankind changes his attitude towards the environment. The voice accuses women that through "burning down the forest" (24) they (women) "have killed the nerves of the earth" (24) thereby preventing it from normal functioning through the upsurge of climate change and other ills.

Turning to Man whom the voice acknowledges as prince of the soil, the ancestral voice appreciates the role of Man in making rain to fall, streams to flow, air and light. The prince of the soil is however accused of having "hunted all the animals in the land, killed the antelope and its child to eat". (24) The voice notes that all these mishaps have been as a result of human mankind's ignorance about sustainable development of environmental species. Hence the question: "what have you left on the earth to multiply? Which animals shall your off springs see, taste and worship the wonders of the earth"? (24) The voice

accuses Esei of killing the “raffia bush, the Cassa mango and the Abobong trees to plant the red man’s cocoa and coffee” (24) All these accusations are meant to bring Mankind to consciousness about sustainable use of the environment and its species. The above accusations show that mankind is at the centre of all the environmental hazards. His/her activities on land consciously or unconsciously are the root cause of environmental degradation. Nduge et al. argue in the same line of thought, warning about the need to protect the environment as they write:

The climate is changing. The earth is warming up and there is now overwhelming scientific consensus that it is happening and human beings are facing the consequences. With global warming on the increase and species and their habitat on the decrease, chances for ecosystem to adapt naturally are diminishing. (2009, p.1)

If climate is changing and the earth is warming it is amongst other things caused by deforestation without replanting new trees. This practice over the years, results to depletion of the ozone layer, more accumulation of greenhouse gases and many more undesirable hazards on the earth and the atmosphere. These scholars (Nduge et al) recommend mankind’s consciousness to combat the changing trends of the rich environment as the only way to repair the damage caused. In fact, global warming, caused partly by excessive logging is fast diminishing both the human and the non-human species. Perhaps the training of forest guards should be made more intensive with the provision of the required tools to enable an effective execution of their duties.

The Lack of environmental consciousness, greed, capitalism, unquenchable thirst for power and many more pseudo environmental practices result to an almost complete destruction of the natural environment of Allehtendurih people led by an autocratic and intransigent leader Akeumbin. A prompt ancestral intervention through a voice nevertheless helps to curb the imminent calamity.

2.2 Curbing Human Calamity in the Environment

The effects of unhealthy Behavior of Nkengasong’s characters towards their environment (Allehtendurih) are quite challenging, showing how mankind needs to intensify his relationship with nature or become more environmental friendly as a way forward in curbing human calamity in the land. The following illustrations depicting the attitude of the different characters in *Ancestral Earth* towards their environment and the species therein will discuss this further.

The destruction of the forest through the ‘red men’, who cut the wood for timber; the farmers who cut the wood for agriculture, both leave the land barren and bare. As a result economic activities are slowed down due to poor yields, citizens resorting to other unorthodox practices like poaching, excessively drinking of palm wine with their little earnings. In fact poor habits take an alarming rate amongst the people. M’meke decries such habits in these words:

... We suffer to feed our homes. Even when the soil frowns at us! My own husband! You will find him in a matango house, drunk with the little money he made from selling a deer he shot yesterday; the only animal he has shot after hunting for so many weeks. He didn't leave any anini in the house for children to eat ... yet he would complain of hunger, beat me and abuse my mother... (4)

Nkengasong uses anthropomorphism (the frowning soil) to describe the distance and inharmonious relationship between the women of Allehtendurih and the soil, a regrettable situation for the livelihood of the people. The above quotation talks of man's unfriendliness to nature and how it is characterized by myriads of multiplier effects such as conflicts, poverty, hunger, health hazards, laziness and above all the absence of love between couples. It should be noted nevertheless that the men of Allehtendurih are advised to engage in other means of livelihood other than poaching. Consequently, if their poverty is as a result of the fact that poaching has failed then it is an encouraging factor. Alternative means of livelihood other than poaching are therefore encouraged. This vividly reveals the inevitability of education for sustainable development in our communities. Education in most communities in Africa needs, amongst other things, to be geared towards environmental sustainability of rare species. There is also the need to reflect on other means of livelihood other than persistently exploiting the endangered species that are fast disappearing and need to be protected.

It is evident from the text under study that species extinction due to over exploitation has become the order of the day in Allehtendurih in particular and most African societies in general. Deforestation (logging) and poaching have contributed to the near extinction of some of the trees and animal species respectively. Eseh, one of the characters in the text, confirms this in these words "I am the hare that used to run faster in the forest; but now the forest runs fastest under my feet. I have hunted the deer for one whole season and I did not see any to shoot before it escaped." (8) This regret from Eseh shows the seriousness with which environmental needs should be tackled. Not only plant species, but some animal species as well have almost gone extinct from the forest. This is the challenge involved in preaching anthropomorphism or sustainable development of species. When species go almost extinct like the deer mentioned above, the younger generation is sacrificed; they may never see such species in their life time.

Ntse, one of the closest collaborators of the Fon confirms the disappearance of some environmental species due to deforestation. Talking about streams, Ntse notes that the trees that milk the streams at the catchment have been killed. And the lakes are muddy. "The earth bleeds, and the streams have the colour of an old wound: the water tastes like liquid from an old wound. And when you drink your belly rumbles gbru like a water fall, and all kinds of illnesses arrest you at the instant". (9) The catastrophic nature of deforestation is made evident through this quotation which anthropomorphically talks of the bleeding of the earth to reveal human destructive activities on it. It can also be described as human irrationality towards this natural resource. More so, Streams dry off

and the quantity that is left is dangerous for human health, due to its colour and taste. The fact that streams dry off and the little available water causes health hazards summarizes all these undesirable effects of deforestation in our environment and in the species therein. Catchment areas are water sources. Such environments need protection from hazardous environmental crisis. In fact the water disappears in most cases. Long term engagement in replanting the trees seems to be the only panacea to the fast degrading Allehtendurih environment. Nduge et al, further intimate and corroborate in this regard as they write:

When trees and forest are destroyed or cut down, carbon is released back into the atmosphere, causing more carbon dioxide into the air, making the atmosphere warmer than before. This will then lead to drought and desertification which largely affects the earth resulting to famine, wind, storm, prevalence of disease and a host of other catastrophes. (2009, P.27)

This quotation echoes the devastating consequences of indiscriminate destruction of trees and forest often for selfish capitalistic interest of a few individuals. If the people of Allehtendurih complain of health hazards as evident in the text, it is partly due to the rate at which they have destroyed their forest. It is as a result of this that I strongly recommend intensification of education for sustainable development of natural species in our different environments and African communities.

Arguing on air pollution, lebu reveals how the sky is damaged due to industrial and other unhealthy activities of mankind in the environment such as burning of waste and bush fire.

Lebu argues that;

The sky is thin, the air is heavy. All the smoke of burning and toxic matter have invaded the air; all the smells of bad things stand stiff in the air, and there is little rain in the sky... for many moons I have sneezed and coughed .I am almost chocking. (9)

Air pollution is one of the main sources of environmental health hazards .The effects of air pollution as explained by lebu in the quotation above, needs much to be desired as the fight for environmental protection continues. Deforestation, accompanied by nations' competitive industrialization, the quest for capitalism, and other pseudo environmental strategies to reign supreme at the political, social and economic realm at the international scene has resulted to a series of undesirable environmental challenges which among other things include: greenhouse gases accumulation, depletion of the ozone layer, drought in many parts of the world today and more hazardous occurrences. Mafua corroborates this when she notes that: "The heat of the sun has brought our children many fevers and we can no more find the medicinal herbs in our bushes to squeeze into their eyes and nostrils."(13) If there is the heat of the sun as noted above, it is because of deforestation which comes with its undesirable hazards. Even nature seen through medicinal herbs, which acts as a cure to some of these illnesses has been destroyed through all forms of

logging and at times bush fire. When Fon Akeumbin declares that “I have, with my foreign friends cut down the forest and opened the land so that you can work freely on the soil”, (13) he is testifying his role towards the destruction of nature (trees) in Allehtendurih and towards bringing in disease, famine, and conflict. It is also a strategy of domination and continuous exploitation of African resources by the Whiteman in the postcolonial era.

Thanks to Alibi’s narrative, we are made to understand that the country was once proud of rich natural species, but due to the poor management of the resources and its unsustainable exploitation, the people cannot boast of anything at the moment. Hence Alabi questions: “Akeumbin answer me straight: Is this Allehtendurih whose land was filled with the wealth of nations, on whose mountains the leopard snarled with pride and the lions roared with verve in the jungle”?(16) Through this quotation, it is made clear that a number of animal species have almost gone extinct in Allehtendurih. All these are attributed to the pseudo environmental strength of the leaders like Akeumbin. They ignorantly exploit the species without considering its sustainability. They are also selfish, ego centric and poorly informed on environmental exigencies. M’meke further echoes as a way of decrying man’s activities on mother earth, the disappearance of some important natural species thus:

There is no life in the bushes The many coloured birds that twitter in the undergrowth, the young moles that raced through the earth, the deer that dreamt all day under the shade chewing the cud, the leopard that walked with majesty from jungle to jungle and the lizard nodded with adoration from crack in the tree These and many other wonders on the bosom of the earth are seen no more. (17)

Mankind’s anthropocentric consciousness towards the natural species as seen above is challenged by ecocritics who preach species sustainable development. The fact that most of the natural species that used to parade the environment are seen no more reveals humankind’s unhealthy relationship with the environment. The forest which is supposed to act as a reservoir and a sacred habitat to the myriad and varied environmental species is fast losing its potentials in this regard due to mankind’s unethical activities therein. Humanity needs to re-think the best way possible to preserve the existing natural species from further extinction through human exploitation. Consequently Alabi does not hide his feelings to remind Fon Akeumbin in these words: “Akeumbin, you are the traitor to the children of Allehtendurih you have sold their land because of greed and wickedness”. (17-18) Self-centeredness of Fon Akeumbin has taken precedence over social collectivity and environmental sustainability. He re-iterates that “the children of Allehtendurih need the milk of the raffia palm to make their limbs strong. They need the fruit of the wild trees that made them survive the fever.” (24) But how can this be achieved when the plants are all being destroyed through human greed and self-centeredness?

The people's inability to ensure sustainability is captured by the voice as it questions: "What have you left for the children of Allehtendurih?" (24) This question which is directed towards the leadership of the land (Allehtendurir), reminds mankind to be environmentally friendly; to leave a legacy or ensure posterity, sustainability in environmental management and other developmental needs of the people. All these culminate in solving the problems that emanate from the general cry concerning poor environmental protection. This is because it is relatively easy to destroy the environment but quite difficult to build it back. Shipley et al confirm this as they write: "there is of course no doubt that man's capacity for altering the biosphere is greater than his ability to control the changes he has brought about" (1996 p.37) This quotation is quite appropriate in explaining the realities in Allehtendurih in particular and other African communities in general. If today there is the cry of global warming, species lost, ozone layer depletion, increase floods, landslides, earthquake occurrences and many more undesirable crises the world over, it is because a few unscrupulous individuals have consciously or unconsciously destroyed the land often for selfish gains.

In another action, Alabi rebukes Fon Akeumbin for destroying nature in these words: "You have destroyed the jungle, Akeumbin and so there can be no lions" (20), it reminds us of Akeumbin's lack of biocentric consciousness. Akeumbin's anthropocentric world view through the way he destroys the environment is a cause for concern. This statement also signals the near extinction of some species like lions and other endangered animals species in the wilderness. It is in this connection that the children of Allehtendurih visit ancestors of the land to plead on them for more blessing as we hear from these utterances by Alabi: "...we have come to tell you that the earth has abandoned us. Our rich black earth bleeds and we feel the pains. Pity us fathers and bring us life again" (23) Due to the people's almost complete disconnection with the environment through their anti-anthropomorphic practices, life has become very hostile. Lebu notes that: "our lives are chocking. Make us breath again. Give us plenty of harvest time. Give us peace, give us happiness, and give us healthy lives. Give us children, water and air". (23)

Having gained consciousness from the speech made by a voice, Fon Akeumbin decides that he and the children of Allehtendurih should feed the earth as a way of seeking for peace; not by using animal in sacrifices as has been the case before, but by planting trees. He announces that a day shall be designated whereby "All the sons and daughters of Allehtendurh shall feed the earth with seeds, plants and stem. And we shall plant them all over the barren land of allehtendurih. Go now...." (25) This proposal by Akeumbin is a wonderful contribution intended to be used in booting environmental prowess. This practice, it is hoped, will restore the lost glories and heritage of the land of Allehtendurih on human, animal and plant species. It also signals the rebirth of hope for the community. We only hope that this should be accompanied by strict control on logging as well.

The absence of environmental consciousness has gotten a lot of multiplier effect at so many levels: health hazards, conflict, poor harvest, and other undesirable occurrences. All these are characterized by mankind's unhealthy attitude towards the earth. Esei therefore pleads for a change in these words: "... drive away the heat of the earth. Make the rain to fall, and crops grow. Let us meet partridges on their eggs, and not the tigress on its cubs. Give us abundance till you call us to live with you in the earth". (23) These words which are meant to appease the earth remind humanity the extent to which he/she has gone down the drain in degrading the environment and its species. It also captures the extent to which mankind's self-centeredness towards the environment has distorted the species cycle, characterized by a series of hazards like: global warming resulting from bush fires, indiscriminate hunting which may result to extinction of species for posterity. It situates the indisputable role of mother earth. We were created out of it; as human beings, it provides us with food and other fundamental needs and when we are dead we go back to it. Humanity should therefore treat the earth fairly. Rubin, 2008, corroborates this argument when he writes that:

There is now considerable evidence that humanity has altered the biophysical system of earth, not just the carbon cycle which has been the focus of much recent politics, but also the nitrogen cycle and ultimately the atmosphere and climate of the whole globe. (2008, P.23)

Robin feels that as Mankind needs comfort in nature for healthy bodies, he should be able to preserve and nurture it for posterity. The idea of threatening and destroying environmental natural species for different selfish glories is really showing mankind's imposing, domineering and anthropocentric nature towards other non-human species. Through this practice of human intransigence, man is unconsciously providing the knife for his own assassination. As a result of all these mishaps, the voice roared, intimating that the earth is hungry for replenishment of what has been drained from it. Hence when Akeumbin regains consciousness and embarks on feeding the earth known to the people as "liukseih" (25) through tree planting exercise by all Allehtenduriah sons and daughters, hope is once more rekindled in the land.

3 Methodology

A qualitative interpretative method of the analysis of the literary work was effected to give an insight into the critical overview of the issues and concerns under study. The method used in gathering material for this study is documentary research namely library research. In this regard, a lot of reading was carried out on environmental literature and ecocriticism; the latter being the literary critical theory used in the analysis of the work. In doing research to enhance the definition of key concepts like "anthropomorphism" and "green economy", used in the study, library research was employed. Similarly, literature was reviewed. There was the need to do a conceptual and an empirical review of literature. This necessitated an extensive library research on the basic concepts evident in the topic like "Anthropomorphism" and "green economy" and also to read works so far

written on the corpus (Ancestral Earth) under study respectively. Through this, the researcher was able to carve out his own niche for this study and in this area of research. Books, dissertations, periodicals, as well as other published and unpublished works were consulted both in the book shelves and online.

4 Conclusion

The study was a reading of Nkengasong's *Ancestral Earth* with the intention of investigating the extent to which ecocentric consciousness has impacted society through the author's craftsmanship. It argued that through *Ancestral Earth*, Nkengasong is able to reveal the extent to which mankind has either consciously or unconsciously destroyed the natural environment and its species for selfish short-lived glories which are either political social or of economic interest. As a result, humanity ironically suffers setbacks in term of health hazards, conflicts, poverty, hunger, species lost and its consequences and a lot more undesirable effects. This conflict in Allehtendurih is represented on the one hand by the Fon and his "red friends" (a neo-colonial leadership) and on the other hand by women and notables of Allehtendurih. These two classes of people have used action, debate, setting, different props as well as different and varied members of the cast to propose way forward on how the land should be managed and made more accommodating, more fertile, more resourceful and more sustainable. This anthropomorphic consciousness is the crux of the matter in this study. Anthropomorphism kills intrigues, dictatorship, ego centrism, greed, avarice, and illiteracy especially when it concerns human relationship with environment. The place of the supernatural forces (the voice) in ensuring lasting peace is timely and appropriate to curb imminent catastrophe. Nkengasong feels that reconciliation between humankind and his environment through ensuring sustainable management of natural species will be quite inevitable for life to blossom once more and to enable man reflect on how to rebuild the memorable past glories.

5 References

Works cited

Primary Source

Nkengasong, Nkemngong. *"Ancestral Earth"*. Bamenda. ANUCAM EDUCATIONAL BOOKS, 2015.

Secondary Sources

Achabe, Chinua. *Things Fall Apart*. London: Heinemann Educational Book Ltd, 1962

Buell, Lawrence. *The Future of Environmental Criticism*. U.S.A: Blackwell publishing Ltd, 2005.

- Dudley, Nigel et al. eds. *Forest Quality: Assessing Forest at a Landmark Scale*. U.K and U.S.A: Earthscan, 2006.
- Efuet, Edward Fomin. "Green Economy and Sustainable Development: An Ecological Reading of Athanasius Nsahlai's *The Buffalo Rider*", *Journal of Tertiary and Industrial Sciences*, Vol. 2 No 2, 2021. P. 85-100.
- Glotfelty, Cheryll and Fromm Harold. Eds "The Ecocriticism Reader: Landmarks in Literary Ecology". University of Georgia Press, 1996.
- Ingram, Merrill et al, eds *Coming into Contact: Exploitation in Ecocritical Theory and Practice*. Athens: University of Georgia Press
- Nduge, Enang Alfred et al. *Learn English, Understand Climate Change Students' Book three*. Cosmos Educational book Ltd, 2009.
- Ngie, Mbobu Florence. "Gender and the Politics of Power/powerlessness in John Nkengasong's *Ancestral Earth*". *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2019.
- Nkengasong, Nkemngong. "Was Anything Wrong with Worshiping Green Gods? Sacred Ecology and Indigenous Environmental Ethics in Cameroonian Writing", *ISLE*, 2020, P.706-725.
- Pagiola, Stefano et al. eds *Selling Environmental Services: Market-based Mechanisms for Conservation and Development*. London and U.S A: Earthscan Publication Ltd, 2002.
- Robin, Libby. "The Eco-Humanities as literature: A New Genre"? University of Queensland Press, 2008.
- Shipley, Helen de Mattes et al. Eds *WWF Challenging worlds 35years of Conservation Achievement*. Switzerland: WWF International, 1996.
- Williams, Raymond. "Ideas of Nature", *Problems in materialism and Culture*. London: Verso, 1980.